

Bachelor's Degree in Computer Engineering
Computer Engineering

Bachelor's Thesis

**Porting and optimization of scientific particle
simulation code**

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Abstract

Starting from a particle simulation program written in Python, this project had two main objectives: porting that code to a faster language C++, and optimizing the resulting code. The motivation behind these goals stems from the execution time limitation on the ATLAS supercomputer from DIPC (Donostia International Physics Center), which is 7 days. The original code was created and owned by ESS Bilbao, a company which focuses its efforts contributing to the European Spallation Source.

The code mainly revolves around the use of a well known free open-source library, FEniCS, which offers a wide range of functionalities, such as solving partial differential equations using the finite element method. Specifically, DOLFIN is used as the interface for the computational back-end of FEniCS, which provides functionality for both Python and C++. Throughout the code, aside from creating the mesh and calculating the RF field density flux functions, DOLFIN is used to determine the force an electron suffers in each step of the execution and to determine if it has collided with the object's inner walls.

Thus, the project consisted on the following different stages: firstly, analyze and understand the original code, then port the code to C++ and check for different execution results. Secondly, analyze which optimization techniques could be implemented using OpenMP and MPI for both multithreading and multiprocessing, and apply those techniques where possible. Lastly, profile the application for further optimization and analysis of results.

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1. CHAPTER

Introduction

ESS Bilbao is a public consortium which focuses its efforts on improving particle accelerator technologies, as well as neutron scattering science. They achieve such goals by contributing to the European Spallation Source (ESS) project, which is currently being constructed in the Swedish city of Lund. Among other things, ESS Bilbao is the main contractor in the Miracles scientific instrument, specializing in the study of polymers and soft condensed matter.

Utilizing a linear pulse accelerator (Linac), ESS is set to become the most powerful pulsed neutron source to date. Numerical simulation is a big part of the design process for such equipment. The original code provided for this project was one of many programs used for those simulations. In this case, a particular physical effect is studied, the Multipactor Effect.

This effect describes the release of secondary electrons when a charged electron collides with an equipment wall under vacuum conditions, in the case of satellites, plasma experiments and particle accelerators, for example. These secondary electrons can then be accelerated by the same RF field, and thus collide again, resulting in an exponentially growing electron cloud [[Ben-Zvi et al., 1973](#)].

This phenomenon can cause malfunction of the component, limit the RF field performance, or even damage the equipment. The simulation's goal is to help determine under which conditions this effect is caused, and for that goal a large number of simulations are required.

These simulations are usually very computationally expensive, not only because of the

vast number of distinct conditions meant to be simulated in different executions but also because of the huge number of electrons that must be simulated in some occasions.

The overall objective was to improve and optimize the original code, so that a higher number of, more complex, or longer simulations could be run in the same execution time as before, maximizing DIPC's ATLAS supercomputer capacity. Since the Python code already had multiprocessing capabilities, the focus shifted into porting the code to C++, a considerably faster programming language, and then applying parallelization using multi-threading (OpenMP) and/or multiprocessing (MPI). This was possible since FEniCS, the library responsible for the core of the simulation, offers both Python and C++ interfaces.

Since I had no prior experience with C++, DOLFIN, and particle simulation, some extra objectives appeared during the project's duration. In conclusion, these were the overall steps and goals of the project, including those that appeared later.

First, a proper environment had to be configured to confirm that FEniCS could be used for both Python and C++ programs. Then, an analysis of the original code had to be carried out with the aim of understanding the logic and functionalities to later port the code.

Then, the first milestone was to write the C++ sequential port. Writing the port was thought to be a straight-up syntax change, but a few challenges rose up, like the environment setup and compilation process, as well as some functions that the FEniCS's Python interface offered but not the C++ interface.

Once the port was working, the next task was to determine if the results generated in both versions were equal; and fixing, or failing that, explaining those differences. Once having the sequential C++ code ready, the next task was to determine which parallelization techniques could speed-up the code, and implement those techniques. The intention was to implement hybrid parallelization techniques involving both the use of OpenMP and MPI, but it was later proved that the use of MPI implied a too fine grain parallelization that would hinder performance. Thus, all parallelization efforts were directed at analyzing and applying the best OpenMP configuration parameters.

Lastly, a comparison between the Python sequential version and the C++ sequential version determined the speedup achieved by porting the code, and then a comparison between the C++ sequential and parallel versions determined the overall speed-up achieved.

2. CHAPTER

Previous work

Nowadays, much research is being carried out on optimizing scientific simulation codes, with particle codes among them ([[Iwasawa et al., 2016](#)], [[Beck et al., 2019](#)]). This work is devoted to improving and optimizing a computer program simulating a particle-scale phenomenon called the Multipactor effect to exploit computational power available in the ATLAS supercomputer of the Donostia International Physics Center.

Key to this topic is Julen Galarza's project entitled "Parallelizacion de codigos cientificos de simulacion de particulas" [[Galarza Burguete, 2022](#)]. He completed his project in 2022, and his work was based on the same original Python program by the ESS Bilbao group. Julen worked on ensuring that the program's execution was deterministic by including a parameter for setting the seed for the random number generator, facilitating recreatability, essential for comparisons in execution time.

He also subjected some parameters, such as logging and plotting, to analysis to find the impact on runtime of the program's execution, hence furthering the possible fields of optimization. The most important contribution of the work done by Julen was its development of multiple versions of parallelized programs. He developed a multithreading version using Python's `ThreadPoolExecutor` and a multiprocessing version using `ProcessPoolExecutor`. Even if this led to some limitations on the multithreading version because of the GIL (Global Interpreter Lock) of Python, the multiprocessing version obtained good speed-ups by running processes independently.

Julen went one step ahead in fine-tuning the parallelization process with his `2Pools` and `OnePool` versions, which distributed the electrons from different power ranges in separate

or unique execution pools. My work is closely related to Julen's, since the original code is the same. However, my project further emphasizes porting the simulation code to C++ for improved system performance. Although Julen's work was vital for optimizing the Python multiprocessing version to obtain the most significant possible speed-up on the ATLAS supercomputer, my project explores the differences arising from using a compiled language like C++ for such performance-critical applications.

The approach initially was to implement both multithreading and multiprocessing in C++, with the goal of surpassing the net speed-ups achieved in the previous study by Julen. Besides the methodological differences, my work also touches on other particular difficulties that I met in the porting and optimization process, and the analysis done by use of profilers to understand better the inner workings of the code. Julen reached a maximum of around $30\times$ speed-up using Python, in the range of 32-48 cores, which was enough for the characteristics of the project.

3. CHAPTER

Project setup

The project went through different development stages, and for each specific stage certain needs had to be met. During the development of the C++ sequential port, fast compiling and multiple executions were needed as the code was being written, same as when checking whether results were equivalent to the original code. For that, the use of my personal computer was considered to be the best option, as fast changes could be made and tested without the overhead of using a workload management tool as in ATLAS.

On the other hand, when inspecting results and calculating speed-ups, ATLAS was to be used. This was mandatory, as the project's main goal was to make the most out of ATLAS' execution power and policies, comparing it to the previous Python code that was run on ATLAS.

Lastly, for optimization objectives, different profiling tools were used, some of which had to be installed, even needing to install drivers. Since the debugging and profiling options ATLAS offers were too limited, the use of another machine was necessary. The personal computer sufficed for some tools such as Intel VTUNE, gprofng or Score-P, but the Intel VTUNE profiler demanded the use of specific processors for deeper analysis, so Priscilla was used, Itelligent Systems Group's (ISG¹) cluster on the Computer Science faculty in Donostia.

¹<http://www.sc.ehu.es/ccwbayes/>

3.1 ATLAS

The main goal being executing the code on ATLAS, DIPC's supercomputer, a proper environment had to be set up. ATLAS works with modules managed by Lmod, an environment module system which allows easy and fast environment changes. Although for certain particular execution tests at the beginning, like executing C++ FEniCS demos, these modules provided sufficient functionality, in later stages of development the use of modules was discarded, due to version mismatches, distinct compiler clashes and lack of some necessary modules.

DIPC's support service was a big help during this stage; they provided extensive explanations in regard of the use of the supercomputer, modules and detailed analysis about how the project could be executed in their system. The previously mentioned issues with the modules could have been resolved if necessary, nonetheless, it was deemed that using conda environments would present an equally efficient solution and require significantly less time for implementation. Conda is a tool similar to Lmod, managing packages, dependencies, and environments for any programming language. It works by creating isolated environments where different packages are installed, and then activating those environments is enough to execute programs without dependency issues with the machine's installed packages.

FEniCS is available as a conda package through the conda-forge service, a GitHub organization that contains over 25k community driven conda recipes ^{2 3}

After creating the conda environment, a trial-and-error process was carried out to install the necessary packages. Then, once having a functional conda environment, the description of the environment was exported to a file, so later on we could use the specification file on any system. As for the Python program, other libraries exclusive to Python were needed. For the purpose of keeping the environment as clean and compact as possible, instead of installing those libraries in the same conda environment, another environment was created.

ATLAS has 334 computer nodes, with various types and characteristics ⁴. During the development of the project, various nodes were used, since comparing the speed-up was not relevant yet. However, during the last stage of the project, when comparing execution

²<https://conda-forge.org/>

³<https://anaconda.org/conda-forge/fenics>

⁴<https://scc.dipc.org/docs/systems/atlas-fdr/>

times between different versions, the same node type had to be used for the results to be fair. Nodes with Intel Xeon Gold E5-2683 v4 processor, 32 cores, and 256GB of memory were used. Other nodes with more or less cores could be used, but less cores would limit the maximum speed-up, and more cores meant longer waiting times, so finding a balance was mandatory. Moreover, since the use of memory is a critical factor when comparing execution times, the whole machine was to be reserved for the execution, because other programs running on the machine could impact the performance, making the results unreliable.

3.2 Personal laptop

For fast compilation and execution tests, my personal laptop was used, an Acer Aspire 3 A315-56-57QZ, with the specs:

- Processor Intel Core i5-1035G1 CPU @ 1.00GHz-3.60GHz, with 4 physical cores and a total of 8 logical threads
- 12GB of DDR4 RAM memory, divided on two modules of 8GB and 4GB
- Sleepy IL V1.19 motherboard
- Linux Mint 19.3 Tricia operating system

At first, it was thought that installing FEniCS on the local machine was the best option, but it proved difficult, since the FEniCS version we were using for both the original and the ported code was the legacy version. This meant that the options presented on the installation guide were not updated since 2019, and among the different methods offered (from source, from Ubuntu packages, Docker version), only the use of a conda environment resulted on a working installation. The added benefit of using a conda environment on the local computer was the easy import/export of said environment among different machines, and the reliability it meant using the exact same environment. It was also partly for these reasons that the use of Lmod modules was discarded in ATLAS.

The use of profilers was done on this machine, too. gprofng was available within the binutils-2.4 package, which could be easily downloaded and built by source. Later, I installed a GUI extension package for gprofng.

Intel offers its own profiler tool, called Intel-VTUNE. This tool provided great information on CPU and thread usage, but it was insufficient when identifying OpenMP regions for further analysis.

Score-P was another profiling tool that could provide information about the execution. However, since the use of a conda environment was the only option when executing the program, various compatibility and version mismatch errors rose up, making the use of Score-P for profiling impossible.

3.3 Priscilla

Intelligent Systems Group (ISG) researches machine learning, deep learning, optimization and high performance computing. Priscilla is ISG's cluster. A dedicated node of this cluster was used for Intel-VTUNE and Score-P profilers, since they require installation permissions and specific processor types. This node has the following characteristics:

- Processor Intel Xeon X5660 @ 2.80GHz, with 6 physical cores and a total of 12 logical threads
- 96GB of DDR3 RAM memory, divided on 12 modules of 8GB
- X8DTT-H v2.0 motherboard
- Rocky Linux 9.2 Blue Onyx Tricia operating system

3.4 External libraries and tools

A set of established libraries were used throughout the project for the C++ port. Precisely:

OpenMP is a well-known library which offers its C/C++ API since 1998, used to easily implement shared-memory multiprocessing parallelization. It was used on this project for multithreading parallelization purposes.

BOOST is a group that provides free C++ libraries, developed and maintained by both the Boost organization and community. They aim to provide a wide range of libraries that prove useful for a broad spectrum of applications. In this project, Boost

libraries where used to reference universal constants, such as electron charge, speed of light on a vacuum, or even π .

EIGEN is another well-established library for C++. It offers functionalities that C++ lacks and prove useful when working with linear algebra, providing data structures and operations such as matrices, matrix factorization and Fast Fourier Transform, for example. In this project, it was used for certain variables which FEniCS uses, that need to be a certain data type.

FEniCS is a popular library for implementing and solving partial differential equations using the finite element method. This free and open-source library combines both the flexibility and control of manual implementation with the built-in features that other commercial packages such as *Abacus Unified FEA*⁵ or *Ansys*⁶ offer, making it the perfect tool for a wide range of researchers.

FEniCS is a conglomerate of different packages, mostly developed and maintained by the FEniCS project group. Each package or component is responsible for certain aspects of the whole process⁷.

Here is the explanation for the most relevant components for the scope of this project:

- **UFL** (Uniform Form Language) is a specialized language used to declare finite element forms. Providing an easy way to select finite element spaces nearly resembling mathematical notation.
- **FFC** (FEniCS Form Compiler), translates high-level forms defined using UFL into low-level efficient C++ code, in **UFC** format (Unified Form-assembly code).
- **DOLFIN** is a C++/Python interface that acts as a computational backend for FEniCS, inter-operating its distinct components and also communicating with other external libraries; e.g. PETSc, Eigen, MPI and SCOTCH. It provides data structures and algorithms, finite element meshes, among other functionalities.

Since 2019, the fundamental components of the FEniCS project have been extensively restructured, resulting in the development of DOLFINx (along FFCx),

⁵<https://www.3ds.com/es/productos-y-servicios/simulia/productos/abaqus/>

⁶<https://www.ansys.com/>

⁷<https://web.archive.org/web/20111104045327/http://fenicsproject.org/about/components.html#core-components>

a newer version that implements new functionalities and fixes known bugs from the legacy version. DOLFIN is still available for installation and has extensive documentation on the web, but it is no longer maintained. Despite DOLFINx being recommended over DOLFIN⁸, since the original Python code for this project used the legacy version, this project was developed using the same legacy version.

Slurm As ATLAS is a shared supercomputer, resources must be shared as equally as possible, and Slurm is in charge of that. Slurm is an open-source software, designed to manage and schedule jobs efficiently across big Linux clusters. It grants users shared (or exclusive) access to computational resources, resolving resource conflicts by maintaining and managing a queue of pending tasks, ensuring fair allocation among users. The wait time for submitting executions was an important factor during the speed-up testing stage.

Intel VTUNE profiler can be utilized to enhance the performance of applications, optimize system performance, and configure systems for HPC, among other uses. It is freely available, but only its latest version, something that will become relevant later in Section 8.1.

GPROFNG is a profiler provided by GNU, very lightweight and command line based, successor to GPROF (GNU Profiler). This older version is not sufficient for OpenMP profiling⁹, so the newer GPROF-NG (GNU Profiler - Next Generation) was used.

Score-P is a software system designed to provide a measurement framework for profiling, event trace recording, and online analysis of High Performance Computing (HPC) applications. While the tool was studied, installed and tested with a demo, due to incompatibility issues between FEniCS and Score-P, this profiler was not employed on the project's program.

⁸<https://fenicsproject.discourse.group/t/the-new-dolfinx-solver-is-now-recommended-over-dolfin/8249>

⁹<https://stackoverflow.com/a/36939725/16300640>

4. CHAPTER

Analyzing and understanding the original code

The Multipactor Effect, or Multipactor Discharge, is an already well-known and studied phenomenon, with books and papers dedicated to its study [[Ben-Zvi et al., 1973](#)], [[Shemelin and Belomestnykh, 2020](#)]. When a free electron is accelerated by an RF field under vacuum conditions, it can collide against the surface of the equipment, and depending on various factors, such as surface material, surface condition (coating, cleanliness, and finish properties), angle and energy of impact, it can cause that more than one free electron is detached from said wall. This n number of detached electrons can then be accelerated by the same RF field, and as the process continuously repeats, an avalanche is formed. This avalanche can cause various effects, such as power loss, signal interference, or even making the equipment unusable [[Pérez et al., 2005](#)].

Multipactor experiments are expensive, both time and resource-wise. Moreover, it can be a complex phenomenon that cannot be accurately described analytically for some complicated shapes, therefore a numerical simulation has been proven to be a valuable tool to reduce costs and sometimes even the only way to determine whether a multipactor discharge is prone to occur within a set of conditions [[Kravchuk et al., 1999](#)].

These simulations can be developed through different approaches, such as Discrete Event Simulation (DES) [[Fajar et al., 2018](#)], or by managing electrons collectively instead of individually. In this case, electrons were coded to be single independent objects, using a continuous simulation approach, where each time 'step', the forces acting upon the electron are calculated and then it's speed and position values are updated. If the electron collides, a formula is used to determine what chance of secondary electrons are detached.

4.1 Program structure

The structure of the Python code that I was provided with is as follows:

- **bin**: Folder containing the Python execution files.
 - *mpc_run.py*: File that reads the parameters for execution from an external file, initializes them, and then starts the simulation located in *mpc_dolfin.py*.
 - *parameter_list.py*: file that contains information about what data type the parameters from the external file are.
 - *mpc_dolfin.py*: This file has all the functions for the simulation. Most notably, those described later in Listings 4.1, 4.2 and 4.3.
 - *mpc_dolfin_run_mp.py*: file that has the corrected multiprocessing version written by [Galarza Burguete, 2022].
- **data**: Folder that contains mesh-related files.
 - **.txt files*: Files that describe the RF field along the mesh. These files contain thousands of lines, each having six to nine columns. For the first three columns, a 3D point's coordinates are given. For the next three lines, the electromagnetic forces in each axis are given for that 3D point in volts per meter. The last three columns, only present in some of the mesh RF field description files (later seen Figure 4.1), give the values for the magnetic flux density at that point in teslas. These files also contain information about the equipment model, version, date of file creation, dimensions and node quantity.
 - **.h5 files*: Mesh information files, using the HDF5 format. Hierarchical Data Format version 5 (HDF5) is a widely used file format, data model and library. It is designed to handle large amounts of heterogeneous data, aiming to provide portability, fast I/O manipulation and keeping metadata together with the data. It is a binary file format only readable by machine, designed keeping efficiency in mind.
- **generated_files**: Folder where all log files are stored.
- **mpc_run.py**: A soft link that points to *bin/mpc_run.py*. It is used to submit the job using Slurm from the directory where the soft link is, since the program follows a strict structure when using some files, and otherwise it can not find them.

- **mpc_dolfin_run.py**: A soft link that points to `bin/mpc_dolfin_run_mp.py`. It is necessary for visibility when submitting a job using Slurm in ATLAS, since the program handles file paths in a specific manner and needs to be executed from the parent folder, not bin folder.
- ***.mpc files**: Files containing all the parameters for the execution.
- **setup_atlas_example.sh**: An execution submission example script for Slurm, very similar to the one appearing later on Listing 5.6.

4.2 Three different mesh files

There are three different mesh files. The first represents a 3D coaxial piece of model `coaxial_103mm_704MHz`, similar to a hollow cylinder as seen in Figure 4.1, piece that was initially provided for testing. This piece has 3885 nodes.

Figure 4.1: Three different mesh types

Later, other two mesh files were provided: `pikachu_couplers_testbox_500k.mphxtxt` and `pikachu_couplers_testbox_900k.mphxtxt`. They provide the mesh models of the same RFQ (Radio Frequency Quadrupole) power couplers, with different number of definition (nodes). These couplers are components used in linear particle accelerators to transfer power to the beam. ESS Bilbao has developed these "Pikachu" models as part of their testing and improvement processes for RFQ components. The "Pikachu 500k", illustrated in Figure 4.1, features a mesh with 500k tetrahedrons and 100,553 nodes, while the "Pikachu 900k",

also illustrated on Figure 4.1, has a larger mesh with 900k tetrahedrons and 177,897 nodes. These simulations are vital for understanding the behavior and performance of RFQ power couplers in particle accelerators.

The execution tests for calculating the speed-up and efficiency were performed on the three different mesh types, as they offer varying levels of model complexity. The most upfront factor to keep in mind when distinguishing between these mesh files is the size of the models, where cache memory needs and behaviour differs.

4.3 Code parameters

The file used for execution, mentioned on 4.1, contains the full list of parameters needed for execution. The parameters that hold the biggest impact on the duration of the execution are the **simulation_type**, that determines what type of simulation among three options is performed (later explained on 4.4) and **N_max_secondary_runs**, which determines how many generations are going to be simulated. There is another stochastic parameter, the **random_seed**, that can heavily influence execution. This is because in certain cases, depending on the sequence of random number generation, the multipactor effect could not occur, and the execution ends in a matter of seconds.

4.4 Program operation

Depending on the simulation mode, we can simulate a single electron until collision. This is done by function `track_1_e`. The pseudocode for this function is presented on Listing 4.1.

Listing 4.1: *track_1_e* pseudocode

```
1 input: E
2 output: collision, energy, phase, trayectory
3 begin
4     while !ended
5         update_position(E)
6         ended = collision(electron)
7 end
```

In the loop, each 'time step', the forces acting upon the electron are calculated, making use of DOLFIN and the previously initialized electromagnetic functions. Then, according to these forces, the electron's velocity is updated along with its position.

In each step, DOLFIN is again used to check if the new position corresponds to a border in the mesh, meaning that the electron has collided with the equipment. If true, certain calculations are made with regard to the energy and phase in the moment of impact to return those values. If false, the loop continues until it collides further down the trajectory or until a previously defined time limit is reached.

As is later seen thanks to profiling tools, the majority of execution time in the program is used in these two DOLFIN uses: calculating the forces suffered and calculating if a collision occurred.

The other two methods involve multiple electron simulations. On **single electron multipacting** simulation mode, a single electron is initialized, and then that electron, and all subsequently generated electrons, are simulated generation for generation. A generation is the set of electrons generated by the collision of all the electrons of the previous generation. In other words, if a generation has n electrons, all the secondary electrons generated in those n possible collisions are added to the next generation. This is done by function `run_n_electrons_parallel`. The pseudocode for this function is presented on Listing 4.2.

Listing 4.2: `run_n_electrons_parallel` pseudocode

```
1 input: power, [pool_runs], [pool_phase], [pool_energies]
2 output: last_gen_electrons, total_electrons
3 begin
4     for generation in 0..max_generations
5         for e in pool_runs
6             collision = track_1_e(e)
7             [e'] = total_secondary_electrons(collision)
8             [new_pool_runs] += [e']
9             [pool_runs] = [new_pool_runs]
10    end
```

For each individual electron simulation, the starting point in the mesh, the initial phase and the initial energy are required. The `run_n_electrons_parallel` function takes a list for each of these aspects and returns the number of electrons in the last generation, along the number of electrons simulated in total. All electrons in this function are simulated

using the same power value for the RF field. For each generation, and until the maximum number of generations is reached, a for loop iterates over the three lists, simulating each electron using the previously explained function `track_1_e` on Listing 4.1.

The newly detached electrons are calculated by using function `total_secondary_electrons`. The number of these electrons can vary, as it is a stochastic process, but generally ranges between 1 and 6. When all electrons on the current generation have been simulated, the new generation is taken as the current generation, and the process repeats.

Lastly, if the **power range** simulation mode is selected, a previously defined number of initial electrons are generated for each power, and `run_n_electrons_parallel` is called for each power. The pseudocode for this function is presented on Listing 4.3.

Listing 4.3: `run_power_range` pseudocode

```
1 input: [power]
2 output: [last_gen_electrons], [total_electrons]
3 begin
4     for p in power
5         result = run_n_electrons_parallel(p)
6         [last_gen_electrons], [total_electrons] += result
7     end
```

The function responsible for simulating the power range and single-electron trajectory modes is the same: **run**. For each mode of simulation, the list of power values has a different length, being one element for *single electron multipacting* and more than one for *power range*.

In other aspects, despite being very similar to the pseudocode on Listing 4.2, the main difference is that the starting electrons are many, not only one, and they are randomly generated before calling the function `run_n_electrons_parallel`.

5. CHAPTER

Writing the C++ sequential port

The writing of the sequential port was mostly straightforward, a syntax change. However, three aspects are worth mentioning about this process: the parts of the code that were not ported, or that they were ported differently; a couple of bugs found on the Python code and some functions that the DOLFIN Python interface offered, but not the DOLFIN C++ interface.

5.1 Ported differently or not ported

Certain parts of the code were cut off when writing the C++ port. The reason behind was that those parts were never executed based on the parameters of the execution test files. Most of these cut parts were either very subtle changes or mathematics/physics-related code that simplified the code a lot, so, for the sake of maintaining a clearer code, they were cut off. The changes were as follows:

- On `track_1_e` function, we can have a `starting_point` passed to `track_1_e` or not. `starting_point` is a structure that contains the position in 3D, and the initial velocity of the electron. On the files used for the execution tests it never has a starting point. Moreover, since it used *relatively* complex structures (*Eigen :: VectorXd* instead of a *std :: vector*), it was decided to be cut off.
- On the same function, `track_1_e`, when calculating the forces the RF field exerts on the electron, three RF field functions are used, *campoEx*, *campoEy*, and *campoEz*.

These functions are evaluated at the position of the electron, and thus we get the forces for each axis on that point. If a variable called 'magnetic_field_on' is set to true, that is, if aside from a RF field, we have a magnetic field activated inside the equipment; another force affects the electron, and it is defined by functions *campoBx*, *campoBy*, and *campoBz*.

However, in the original code, despite mentioning and using those functions, they are never initialized. Also, the magnetic_field_on variable is never mentioned in the files used for the execution tests.

Instead of deleting the part of the code corresponding to 'magnetic_field_on == true', the approach was to implement that part of the code using *campoEx*, *campoEy*, and *campoEz* instead, to make a possible future implementation of *campoBx*, *campoBy*, and *campoBz* easier.

- Function *closest_entity* calculates what entity is the closest to the point given. It also stores the result on a dictionary, so if a point is more or less similar to a point previously evaluated (with 4 decimal threshold in 3 axes), the calculation is skipped. Originally, both the closest entity and the distance to the entity are returned. Since the entity is non important, only the distance is needed to determine if the electron is inside the mesh or not (to get its initial conditions and force it to be launched inwards from the equipment surface), the C++ port only returns the distance. This simplifies the dictionary too, having a dictionary defined as `std::map<std::string, double>` instead of having to define a more complex `std::map<std::string, std::pair<unsigned int, double>>`
- Another aspect that was cut off was the plotting option. Since the main objective of the project was to optimize and speed-up the code, this functionality is not in the scope of the project. Also, since I had no prior experience with C++ 3D visualization tools, implementing this functionality on the port was discarded.

Moreover, the visualization part of the code on the Python program uses a file generated on execution time, and since the same file is generated on the C++ version, this chunk of code was isolated on its own Python program, and visualization is possible for the C++ execution results too.

5.2 Bugs on the Python code

The Python program used a file called `parameter_list.py`. It describes what data types are the parameters on the execution file. Then, the main program processes the execution file line by line, storing the values for each parameter based on the type of data that the parameter represents based on the information on `parameter_list.py`.

This file holds a list for float parameters, another list for integer parameters, and so on. Inside the `float_arguments` list, `rf_frequency` had lowercase 'rf'. However, in the main code, when this value is processed, it is referenced using uppercase. This caused the program to not register the value of the `RF_frequency` correctly, thus causing different execution values when later comparing the C++ to the Python version, despite having the same `RF_frequency` values on the execution file.

Another bug that caused different values to appear when analyzing differences on the code was on the previously mentioned `starting_point`. Having an `starting_point` means having the 3D coordinates and the direction of the electron at time instant zero. If no `starting_point` is given, the electron can start from a given face in the mesh, or from a random one.

On the Python code, if no `starting_point` is given, the differentiation of choosing a random face or not is done by checking if the argument `face_i` is an integer instance or not. This should work, since in the case of not having an initial face, `face_i` would be null, and not a integer instance, thus choosing a random one. However, due to coding errors, the first time this function is called, a `numpy.ndarray` of one dimension is passed to it, containing one integer. This causes the function to start the simulation from a random face, and thus create different results.

These two bugs were fixed on the C++ code.

5.3 Different DOLFIN interfaces for Python and C++

The calculation of `campoEx`, `campoEy` and `campoEz`, used in Listing 4.1 to calculate the forces upon the electron, is done on function `read_field_data`. This function reads the RF field data from a file that contains information about the field in each axis for a set of 3D points. The project has three different RF field information files:

- `coaxial_103mm_704MHz_EB_field.txt`

- `pikachu_couplers_testbox_500k_EB_field_1W.txt`
- `pikachu_couplers_testbox_900k_field_EB.txt`

Which correspond to the three mesh files described on subsection 4.2. These files are written on plain text format, so the handling and processing of these files is straightforward.

A simplified version of the code `read_field_data` is presented on Listing 5.1, where only the calculation of the *campoEz* function is shown, the process is repeated for the other X and Y axes. The function skips the header files, and then reads the information line by line, dividing each line in 6 different vectors, each storing the values for X,Y or Z points, and the corresponding RF field value for each axis on those points. Note that since on the Python code only the real component of the values is used later on, the C++ port only stores the real part.

Listing 5.1: Python *read_field_data* code

```

1      ...
2      datosEB=np.genfromtxt (data_file, skip_header=9, dtype=str)
3      mapping=np.vectorize(lambda t:complex(t.replace('i','j')))
4      datosEB = mapping(datosEB)
5      datosEBn=np.real(datosEB)
6      Z=datosEBn[:,3]
7      EZ=datosEBn[:,6]
8
9      V=FunctionSpace (self.mesh,"CG",1)
10     Fez=Function(V)
11     Fez.vector().set_local(EZ)
12     campoEz=project(Fez,V)
13     campoEz.set_allow_extrapolation(True)
14     ...

```

On the original Python code, a finite element function space of Lagrange family is created using the mesh as base, this is done by DOLFIN's Python interface's function **FunctionSpace**¹ in line 9 of the Listing 5.1. By creating a finite element function space over a mesh, a finite element is associated with each cell of the mesh.

¹<https://fenicsproject.org/olddocs/dolfin/1.4.0/Python/programmers-reference/functions/functionspace/FunctionSpace.html>

Basis functions are a set of functions from which by linear combination any function can be represented. Each finite element has their own basis functions, called local basis functions. The basis functions of the whole function space are called global basis functions. The space function is created with one degree of freedom, that is, with only one basis function.

Later, an empty function is created on the said function space, as seen on line 10. The local basis functions are set on each cell on the next line, by using method `set_local`, and passing the values collected from the mesh information file.

Lastly, on the final two lines, that function is projected and the function space, and extrapolation is enabled. The projection operator is a map that takes a function and returns the closest function within the function space. This closeness is usually defined in terms of a norm or inner product [Brenner, 2008]^{2 3}. Enabling extrapolation means that the resulting function *campoEz* can be evaluated outside of its domain, since during execution the electron may exceed the domain defined on the function.

On DOLFIN's C++ interface, there is no *project* method available, and the function space must be defined 'manually'. This is done using FEniCS's Uniform Form Language (UFL), used to declare finite element forms⁴. That definition is later compiled into a header file using FEniCS Form Compiler (FFC), which translates high-level forms defined using UFL into low-level efficient C++ code⁵.

Since I needed a Lagrange function space, I defined my own in the *MyLagrange.ufl* file, presented on Listing 5.2. FEniCS project has a wide offer of demos on their web⁶ that provide all the necessary components for execution. It is by using the contents of these demos that I built *MyLagrange.ufl*.

Listing 5.2: *MyLagrange.ufl* code

```
1 element = FiniteElement("Lagrange", tetrahedron, 1)
2
3 u = TrialFunction(element)
4 v = TestFunction(element)
```

²[https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Projection_\(linear_algebra\)#Finding_projection_with_an_inner_product](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Projection_(linear_algebra)#Finding_projection_with_an_inner_product)

³<https://fenicsproject.org/olddocs/dolfin/1.5.0/Python/programmers-reference/fem/projection/project.html>

⁴<https://fenics.readthedocs.io/projects/ufl/en/latest/>

⁵<https://fenics.readthedocs.io/projects/ffc/en/latest/>

⁶<https://fenicsproject.org/olddocs/dolfin/2016.1.0/cpp/demo/index.html>

```

5
6 g = Coefficient(element)
7
8 a = inner(u, v)*dx
9 L = inner(g, v)*dx

```

On the first line the function space is created. It is from Lagrange family, and since it represents 3D space, the cell type is tetrahedron, with one single degree of freedom. This directly substitutes the *FunctionSpace* method from the Python interface.

As for the *project* method, a TrialFunction and TestFunction are necessary. Another function is also necessary, in this case, called 'g', which is used for setting the local values from the C++ code, read from the mesh information file. Then, two inner products are defined, a and L. It is by solving an equality between these two functions that the resulting RF field function is achieved. By using FFC, MyLagrange.ufl is compiled into MyLagrange.h. After importing it, it can be used to achieve similar functionality to the Python interface's project method, as seen on Listing 5.3.

Listing 5.3: C++ *read_field_data* code

```

1 ...
2 auto V = std::make_shared<MyLagrange::FunctionSpace>(mesh);
3 auto Fez = std::make_shared<dolfin::Function>(V);
4
5 Fez->vector()->set_local(EZ);
6 Fez->vector()->apply("insert");
7
8 auto campoEz_temp = std::make_shared<dolfin::Function>(V);
9
10 MyLagrange::BilinearForm az(V,V);
11 MyLagrange::LinearForm Lz(V);
12 Lz.g = Fez;
13
14 dolfin::solve(az == Lz, *campoEz_temp);
15 campoEz_temp->set_allow_extrapolation(true);
16 campoEz = campoEz_temp;
17 ...

```

This is also a short version showing the calculation of one of the RF field functions for each axis, *campoEz*. *Fez* is created in line 4, and it will hold the values taken from the file (in lines 6 and 7). The elements of the equality we hope to solve are created on lines 11 and 12, further adding the local values through the use of the previously mentioned *g*. Then, the *dolfin* solver is called, and the result is stored.

5.4 Resulting C++ program structure

The program contains some necessary and optional folders and files. The resulting structure is as follows:

- **build**: Optional folder where the program is compiled. This folder is used to contain all the compilation information for CMake and make. The program could be compiled directly with a single command, or compiled on another folder and then moved to the current folder, hence making this folder convenient yet non mandatory.
- **data**: Compulsory folder that contains the mesh information file, the file that describes the RF field along the mesh, and the file containing all the parameters for the execution.
- **generated_files**: Compulsory folder where all log files are stored.
 - **checkpoints**: Folder containing the checkpoint files, generated periodically and used for resume an advanced execution point if necessary.
- **CMakeLists.txt**: Optional file containing information for compilation using CMake. As stated previously, if compilation is done by command line or on another folder, this file can be discarded.
- **mpc_run**: The program executable binary file.
- **mpc_run.cc**: The source code written in C++, can be discarded if only execution and not compilation is required.
- **MyLagrange.h**: Necessary file for compilation, but not for execution. Contains additional information about the vector space.

- **slurm_execute.sh**: File containing an execution submission example script for ATLAS.
- **slurm_compile.sh**: File containing a compiling submission example script for ATLAS.

5.5 Compiling the code

Compiling the code is only necessary for the C++ port. The compilation process is as shown on Listing 5.4.

Listing 5.4: Compile submission script for Slurm

```
1 module load Python
2 conda activate /scratch/aperez440/fenics-env
3 export CPATH=/scratch/aperez440/fenics-env/include
4 export CPATH=/scratch/aperez440/fenics-env/include/eigen3:$CPATH
5 export LD_LIBRARY_PATH=/scratch/aperez440/fenics-env/lib:$LD_LIBRARY_PATH
6 export PKG_CONFIG_PATH=/scratch/aperez440/fenics-env/lib/pkgconfig:$PKG_CONFIG_PATH
7
8 cd build/
9 rm -r *
10 cmake ..
11 make
12 mv mpc_run ../mpc_run
13 conda deactivate
```

After loading the default Python module using Lmod for conda capabilities, and activating the conda environment, certain paths are exported. These exports make it possible for the compiler to find the necessary libraries and components. The compilation is configured inside the *build* folder using CMake. Later, make is called to compile the code and the executable is moved to the parent folder. This is because how the executable handles paths to the execution, mesh and output files.

On the personal laptop, the steps are the same, except needing to load Python module and changing the paths to the corresponding ones for each particular machine.

5.6 Executing the code

A Slurm submission script is necessary for executing the code, an example script is shown on Listing 5.5

Listing 5.5: Execution submission script for Slurm

```
1  #!/bin/bash
2  #SBATCH --partition=general
3  #SBATCH --qos=regular
4  #SBATCH --job-name=mpc_run
5  #SBATCH --nodes=1
6  #SBATCH --ntasks-per-node=1
7  #SBATCH --cpus-per-task=32
8  #SBATCH --constraint=2683v4
9  #SBATCH --time=16:00:00
10 #SBATCH --error=slurm_output/mpc_run_err.txt
11 #SBATCH --output=slurm_output/mpc_run_out.txt
12 #SBATCH --mem=8000
13
14
15 # modules
16 conda activate /scratch/aperez440/fenics-env
17 export CPATH=/scratch/aperez440/fenics-env/include
18 export CPATH=/scratch/aperez440/fenics-env/include/eigen3:$CPATH
19 export LD_LIBRARY_PATH=/scratch/aperez440/fenics-env/lib:$LD_LIBRARY_PATH
20 export PKG_CONFIG_PATH=/scratch/aperez440/fenics-env/lib/pkgconfig:$PKG_CONFIG_PATH
21
22 export OMP_PROC_BIND=spread
23 export OMP_SCHEDULE="static"
24 time ./mpc_run data/coaxial_704_01.mpc
25 conda deactivate
```

First, a bunch of Slurm parameters are dictated. Different *qos* (quality of service) provide different services. For this task, the *regular* qos is requested, which allows for execution times for up to 24h, up to 24 nodes per user and up to 50 simultaneous jobs per user. Depending on the execution parameters inside the code, the execution time can take from a couple minutes to weeks, but for the average execution this window of 24 hours suffice.

Another Slurm parameter is the *cpus-per-task*. It determines the number of threads the script is requesting. In the example shown on Listing 5.5, one processor node with 32 threads are requested, for a multithreading execution.

The *constraint* parameter in the example is used to ask for certain type of node, in this case *Intel Xeon E5-2683 v4*. This is optional, later on the use of this parameter will be

justified.

The *mem* parameter is optional too, in this case 8GB are requested since the bigger meshes (like the ones shown on Figure 4.1) require more memory than the default amount assigned when no *mem* clause is defined.

Followed by this, the conda environment is activated and two key parameters for OpenMP are configured. These parameters will be later discussed on the results section. The executable is called and an execution file is passed to it, containing the specific parameters for the execution.

On the personal laptop, the process is the same, skipping the Slurm submission script.

For the Python code, the submission script is similar, but not quite the same. An example submission script can be seen on Listing 5.6.

Listing 5.6: Python execution submission script for Slurm

```
1  #!/bin/bash
2  #SBATCH --partition=regular
3  #SBATCH --job-name=mpc_run-original
4  #SBATCH --cpus-per-task=4
5  #SBATCH --nodes=1
6  #SBATCH --ntasks-per-node=1
7  #SBATCH --time=00:30:00
8  #SBATCH --error=original_err.txt
9  #SBATCH --output=original_out.txt
10
11 # modules
12 module load Python
13 conda activate /scratch/aperez440/fenics-env-2
14
15 export DIJITS0_CACHE_DIR="./cache"
16
17 srun python mpc_run.py coaxial_704_01.mpc
```

6. CHAPTER

Analyzing the differences and explaining/fixing them

When executing the C++ and the Python code with the same parameters, different results were achieved. This section will illustrate the thought process for finding out what was the cause behind these non matching results, and the possible fixes for them.

6.1 Different RNG objects

The first idea was that since each program version used its own RNG, different stochastic values were appearing even when using the same seed. The Python version used `numpy.random.randint()` and `numpy.random.rand()` functions, while the C++ version used `rand()` function from the standard library.

On another subject, I had practiced with C code wrappers that let me execute functions that I had previously defined. So, as to follow the same approach, I created a shared library in C++ that would only contain two functions, `srand()` and `rand()`. Using these functions from Python could be done with **ctypes**, a foreign function library that allows for C and C++ compatible data types; or **cython**, an static compiler that allows writing C++ extensions for Python. I chose `ctypes` library in Python for a couple of reasons. First of all, `ctypes` is part of the Python standard, so no additional installation was required, saving time and avoiding possible compatibility issues. Also, unlike `cython`, it works directly with a compiled C++ shared library, without needing to define and compile a `cython` interface. Lastly, `ctypes` follows a pure Python syntax, while `cython` requires specific language.

For these reasons, while it is true that *cython* offers better integration and optimization, for prototyping purposes such as this, *ctypes* was a better option.

The source code for the shared library is just using a wrapper for `srand` and `rand`, calling them `my_srand` and `my_rand`, for easy distinction purposes. This library was compiled using the command:

Listing 6.1: myRand.so compilation command

```
1 g++ -shared -o myRand.so -fPIC myRand.cpp
```

- **g++** compiler is used, the GNU C++ compiler
- The resulting name of the library is defined with **-o myRand.so**, using common naming schemes for libraries
- By using the **-shared** parameter, the compiler will create a dynamic library that can be loaded in runtime by other programs instead of an executable
- By using the **fPIC** parameter, the compiler generates position independent code, which is good for shared libraries because they can be loaded at any memory address

I could load the shared library and then substitute the former numpy RNG like shown on Listing 6.2

Listing 6.2: NumPy RNG substitution

```
1 # original numpy calls
2 numpy.random.seed(seed)      # Setting seed
3 numpy.random.rand()          # Random value [0,1)
4 numpy.random.randint(0,max)  # Random int [0,max)
5
6 ## Substituted with
7 c_lib = ctypes.CDLL("/path/to/myRand.so")
8 cpp_RANDOM_MAX = 2147483647
9
10 c_lib.my_srand(seed)         # Setting seed
11 c_lib.my_rand() / cpp_RANDOM_MAX # Random value [0,1)
```

```
12 c_lib.my_rand() % 20 # Random int [0,max)
```

This was tested with a simple execution, generating 10 random float values and 10 random integers on both C++ and Python, using the same seed, and then checking if the generated values were the same, which they were. Moreover, taking a time measurement for generating random numbers using numpy was considerably slower than using my C++ wrapper. The values on Table 6.1 are the average of 10 time measurements using Python's time library.

Action	Python numpy (s)	Python myRand.so (s)
load library	—	0.0022001
random integer	4.62532e-05	9.77516e-06
random float [0,1)	8.58306e-06	2.62260e-06

Table 6.1: Average time for generating random numbers using numpy or myRand.so

However, even if the same sequence of random numbers was generated, the results were not equal. In fact, with the multithreading execution, another extra issue rose up.

6.2 Breaking sequential equivalence

If the same seed is used, the sequence of random numbers is the same for sequential and parallel executions, because all the threads share the same RNG. The sequential execution is deterministic when using the same seed, because each number from the sequence of random numbers will always correspond to the same electron, and thus creating the same secondary electrons with the same values.

On the multithreading execution, since each generation of electrons is divided among threads, and the exact timing of the threads can not be known, different threads took different values from the RNG sequence and different electrons from the queue. Thus, the secondary electrons generated had different values (number of secondary electrons, energy and so on depend on random numbers). In other words, different numbers from the random number sequence will pair up with different electrons on the queue, altering the results from one execution to another.

This concept is common when parallelizing scientific code, since parallelizing a section with a RNG disrupts sequential equivalence. It is the responsibility of the scientist to demonstrate that the sequential and parallel codes produce the same stochastic process

[Cesare et al., 2020]. Nevertheless, a *srand()* line was added inside the secondary electron yield calculation to ensure that the calculation was deterministic between multithreading executions for the speed-up comparisons, and this line should be commented or removed for real use of the program.

6.3 Different electromagnetic functions

Other aspect of the different results on Python and C++ versions could be the electromagnetic functions. By using HDF5, the variables for the electromagnetic functions can be saved to a file: variables *campoEx*, *campoEy* and *campoEz*, previously mentioned on subsection 5.3. Each version calculates it's own set of these variables, and I write them to distinct files. Later, by using a simple external Python program, I read these variables and compare their values.

The values did not match. This could be caused by two reasons:

- Both versions are not reading the mesh information files with the same precision
- The calculation process for *campoEx*, *campoEy* and *campoEz* is different depending on the programming language.

To begin discarding any of these possibilities, first I tried limiting the precision of all floating point values, rounding up to a certain decimal, both in Python and C++. This did not fix the issue, so next step was checking if the information from the magnetic field was being read the same. These tests were performed on versions that used the same RNG sequence and same simulation for each electron. This stage is when bugs mentioned on section 5.2 were discovered, by logging variable values and meticulously analyzing them.

Iterating the file, the 3D points and RF field values are stored on vectors, so in both versions I wrote the vectors to distinct files in binary, and then again on both version I read all the vectors and compared them. The values read were the same, so with this two checks the first possibility was discarded.

The other possibility was that the 'manual' calculation of these variables was not equivalent (seen on Listing 5.3). Looking at the source code from the Python interface, shown on Listing 6.3, we can see that the calculation is pretty similar.

Listing 6.3: project source code for Python interface

```

1 def project(v, V=None, ...):
2     """Return projection of given expression *v* onto the finite element
3     space *V*.
4     v    a :py:class:`Function <dolfin.functions.function.Function>`
5     V    Optional argument :py:class:`FunctionSpace ...
6     """
7     ... Different return statements not relevant to this case ...
8
9     # Define variational problem for projection
10    w = TestFunction(V)
11    Pv = TrialFunction(V)
12    a = ufl.inner(w, Pv) * dx
13    L = ufl.inner(w, v) * dx
14
15    # Assemble linear system
16    A, b = assemble_system(a, L,...)
17
18    # Solve linear system for projection
19    if function is None:
20        function = Function(V)
21    cpp.la.solve(A, function.vector(), b, ...)
22    return function

```

So, the reason for getting distinct RF field functions lies in another place. To bypass this, we tried exporting the functions from C++ code to a file, and then execute the Python version importing those functions from the same file. Even in that case, with sequential executions using the same RNG sequence, and using same precision by rounding all float variables, the executions were *slightly* different. From the third generations on (on average), the executions start to differ, and then consequently the disparity increases.

In summary, the different results were not because of different RNG objects, for different floating number precision nor because of different electromagnetic functions. Out of options, we assumed that the cause for these different results lied in internal precision, logic and/or representation of both DOLFIN interfaces or because of Python/C++ language differences. This can be further researched in the future, but since similar executions were achieved, for the purpose and scope of this project it was considered acceptable.

7. CHAPTER

Parallelizing the code

7.1 Analyzing parallelization techniques to implement

The program followed the execution described on flowcharts [7.1](#) and [7.2](#). The program first initializes parameters and if the simulation type is set to a single electron simulation, `track_1_e` is called once and then the program is finished. Otherwise, depending on the simulation type, the number of power configurations and initial electrons are set, and then for each power setting the function `run_n_electrons` is called.

This function, checks if the current generation has any electrons first, and if so, it iterates over them using a for loop. For each electron, `track_1_e` is called and if it collides, the secondary electron yield is calculated, adding these new electrons to the next generation. Once all electrons from the current generation are simulated, the next generation is taken as the current one, and this loop continues until the maximum number of generation is achieved or until one generation has no electrons. The flowchart for `run_n_electrons` is detailed on [Figure 7.2](#).

Figure 7.1: Global flowchart

Figure 7.2: run_n_electron flowchart

Later, on Figure 7.3, the flowchart for track_1_e is described. It initializes various values and then enters a loop. This loop continues until the electron has collided or until the maximum simulation time for a single electron is achieved ($t_{max} = \frac{N_{cycles}}{RF_{frequency}}$). For each iteration, the forces suffered are calculated, using DOLFIN library and the already mentioned $campoEx$, $campoEy$ and $campoEz$. Then, the electron's velocity and position are updated. A check is made to see if the new position means a collision occurred, and the loop continues if not.

Figure 7.3: track_1_e flowchart

On the three flowcharts, the parallelizable loops are marked as green rectangles. There is a strategy used for parallelization of particle simulation code [Cesare et al., 2020]:

1. Identify all parallelizable loops in the code, according to a depth-first search strategy.
2. Evaluate the potential performance gain obtainable modifying each parallelizable loop, filtering out those that are not worth the parallelization effort.
3. Make each of the remaining candidate loops self-contained, to remove true data dependencies among different iterations.
4. Use nonparallelizable loops as a reference to implement a checkpointing logic, to support stop-resume behaviour

So, the first step is done in Figure 7.3. The inner-most loop, the one responsible for each time step, takes very little time, and depends on two factors, if the electron has collided or if time has run out. So, it is considered a far too fine grain to be worth parallelizing.

The second inner-most loop, the one that iterates over the electrons on the current generation, is already self-contained. Meaning, the electrons are defined before the loop starts, and they are independent between them. This loop is *embarrassingly parallel* [Herlihy et al., 2020].

The next loop on the hierarchy is the one that iterates over all the generations. This loop would be difficult to parallelize, since each generation directly depends on the one before it. However, taking advantage of the needed barrier between generations to synchronize all generated secondary electrons for the next iteration, a checkpoint logic could be implemented, storing the values for the next generation on a file in case a future execution needs to resume the execution from that point on. Writing the values as the program is being executed would require a critical section to ensure coherence, thus adding unnecessary overhead.

With these factors in mind, two possible parallelizable loops appear. First, each electron is completely independent from the other electrons in the same generation, so they can be massively parallelized. Second, each power value can be parallelized as there is no dependency between power settings.

For the first loop, the relatively short life span for an electron and the large number of electrons would imply using multiple nodes with MPI too expensive in terms of communication and overhead.

On the other hand, using GPUs could be beneficial, but the electrons have greatly different life spans, making it difficult to balance the loads between all the GPU cores. Also, using GPU parallelization needs more complex setup and memory management, and requesting a GPU in ATLAS is more costly than requesting a computer node with multiple cores. Thus, for these reasons, threads were used to parallelize the first loop.

OpenMP was used instead of other multithreading tools like POSIX threads for example. First, ATLAS offers documentation on how to submit jobs that use OpenMP. Second, OpenMP offers automatic load balancing with different directives, which is beneficial since each one of the three mesh files (shown on Figure 4.1) behave differently due to different memory needs.

For the second loop, knowing that the inner-most loop was parallelized using OpenMP,

the idea was to distribute each power setting to a different node using MPI, since it offers scalability and efficiency. By distributing the power values, a *single electron multipacting* simulation could be run in each one. This configuration would allow flexibility when requesting different number of nodes and cores on the Slurm submission script. Also, ATLAS offered documentation on how to run Hybrid parallel code that uses both OpenMP and MPI.

When DOLFIN detects the use of MPI, it automatically divides any mesh that is loaded between all the nodes, and there is no way of avoiding so. Thus, when an electron is simulated and the acceleration must be calculated, in most cases, the processor simulating that electron has a portion of the mesh distinct to where the electron is. To fix this, adding a communication step between all processes to determine which process has the mesh portion corresponding to the position would be necessary, and then make that processor calculate it and send the results. This step would hinder the overall performance heavily, since it would need to be executed at each simulation step, thus adding massive unnecessary overhead. As there is no way of avoiding this mesh distribution, the use of MPI was discarded.

7.2 Changes for parallelizing the code

As mentioned on the previous section, the part of the code that was parallelized using OpenMP was the loop iterating the electrons to be simulated. This loop is inside a parallel region, so all the threads share the current generation for simulation.

Using the `'#pragma omp for'` clause, the electrons on a generation are divided. Before and after this section, critical regions were defined to measure execution time, log necessary information to corresponding files, and to ensure correct memory accesses. Each thread generates their own secondary electrons, and to avoid using locks and control overhead that would be necessary for adding new electrons to a unique shared queue, a private *next generation* list was given to each thread. Then, on the critical section, the lists are merged so all threads can share electrons on the next iteration.

During all this process, only one thread, the master thread, prints information about the execution and stores logging information. It also takes the next merged generation and stores it as the current generation, for the next iteration (generation) of the loop. Because time measurements are important, not only a single thread had to be responsible for this

logging process, but it also had to be always the same. The only clause for that in OpenMP is the master clause.

The time it takes to merge together the private *next generation* electron lists was considered, because as the number of electrons increased, it could cause longer and longer overhead. The use of a deque was considered. A deque is usually implemented as a dynamic array, and it represents a double-ended queue, allowing the queue to expand from the front and the back. Because of its definition, unlike vectors that need to be reallocated when changing size, deque can maintain fixed $O(1)$ time for adding any number of electrons to the end of the queue: it only needs to modify a pointer from the end of the queue to the start of the added queue, regardless to the length of the added queue.

In fact, it is stated in the C++ standard that:

"vector is the type of sequence that should be used by default. ... deque is the data structure of choice when most insertions and deletions take place at the beginning or at the end of the sequence"

For this specific use, the list of newly generated secondary electrons is always added to the end of the queue. After taking various time measurements, it was considered not necessary, since it makes the code more complex and the time difference is not so big using *insert()* function from the standard C++ vector for the amount of electrons we are working with on the average execution. Also, clearing the vector takes considerably longer time using deque, thus compensating for the time difference, making it not worth the change ¹.

After some fatal errors appearing when first parallelizing the code using OpenMP, we learned that DOLFIN is not a thread-safe library. So, we tried using critical sections for each call that was done against the DOLFIN library, but that turned the code slower than the sequential version, which is understandable since the majority of execution time is spent on DOLFIN instructions (as seen later on section 8.1). Making a copy of heavy DOLFIN objects can take some time in some cases (proportional to the size of the used mesh), but it performs better than using critical sections on DOLFIN calls.

So, instead, we created a parallel version of each function that used DOLFIN calls. This way, each thread would create a copy of the objects causing the error, and then call those new functions and passing the object to be used by parameter. When in some occasions a sequential version of a function is needed, and in other occasions a parallel

¹<https://www.codeproject.com/Articles/5425/An-In-Depth-Study-of-the-STL-Deque-Container>

version is needed, it is recommended to keep two versions instead of merging it to one [Cesare et al., 2020], so for each function that uses a DOLFIN variable, a copy that takes the DOLFIN object from parameter was created, adding *_thread* to the name of the function.

Another added functionality during this process was the checkpoint logic. Before any generation is simulated, the master thread checks if the use of checkpoints is needed, and if so, reads the contents from the specified file to program memory. Since this is done only once at most, and it is designed to not repeat executions that have reached timeouts, the overhead time of this operation is non relevant.

Then, between each generation, if the generation of checkpoints is needed, it writes the contents to a file. Since this is a relatively frequent operation (depending on the seed a 24h execution can have 4,8 or more than 1024 generations), the time overhead impact of writing the contents to a file has been studied on Table 7.1. The values are the average for 5 different executions. *std::ofstream* is used in binary for better performance.

Gen	#Electrons	Gen time (s)	Checkpoint time (s)	time % for checkpoint
1	4	0,01	0,00333	25,8685%
2	10	0,11	0,00032	0,3014%
3	19	0,10	0,00011	0,1100%
4	40	0,19	0,00022	0,1172%
5	77	0,41	0,00011	0,0273%
6	162	0,60	0,00007	0,0120%
7	334	1,50	0,00006	0,0039%
8	745	2,82	0,00010	0,0036%
9	1596	7,80	0,00007	0,0009%
10	3541	15,00	0,00009	0,0006%
11	7817	31,20	0,00010	0,0003%
12	17324	66,00	0,00019	0,0003%
13	3862	150,00	0,00056	0,0004%
14	85505	396,00	0,00095	0,0002%
15	191302	900,00	0,00202	0,0002%

Table 7.1: Time for each generation vs time for storing checkpoint

We can see that at first, the creation of the checkpoint file is near a 25% of added time to each generation. As the number of electrons increase, the time needed to create the checkpoint file and store the values increases too, but the percentage of time in relation to the time needed to simulate the generation becomes negligible.

Lastly, the parallelization of the power ranges was not considered necessary in the case

of not using MPI, since we can put all the threads to their best use with this *EP* loop, instead of having to store the information of each generation in parallel as to print it later sequentially. In the Python version this functionality was useful, this is because on average, on the Python version, the first generations have a small number of electrons, so most of the cores would remain idle. However, on the C++ version, the number of electrons increases much sooner, so the time spent idle is less in proportion.

Another difference is that the electrons in the Python version have a wider range of lifespans. Meaning that the total number of time steps has a bigger standard deviation than the electron on the C++ version, as seen on Figure 7.4. This can cause various cores to be idle at the end of the generation simulation while some few cores are still simulating long-lived electrons. This phenomenon can occur on both versions, but it's more probable in the Python version for the discussed reasons. Thus, the *onePool* Python version proves beneficial, as the idle cores can take electrons from other power settings, while in the C++ it would prove to be less worth it for the memory and complexity overhead.

Figure 7.4: Histogram showing number of electrons per different time

8. CHAPTER

Code optimization through profiling tools

8.1 Intel VTUNE

The installation of this profiler is straight-forward on Unix based systems. I initially installed the profiler on my personal laptop, getting the installation script from the official website ¹. Then, it was a matter of just executing the script for installation.

After navigating to the installation folder and executing the vtune-gui executable, a new analysis can be configured. There are a lot of different types of analysis, such as micro-architecture, I/O, accelerator, algorithm or parallelism analysis. This last section is the most relevant for this project. In this section, a threading or HPC performance analysis are offered. However, as recommended on Intel's tutorials ², a performance snapshot analysis gives a broad overview of the whole execution.

The two Figure 8.1 suggests that three more analysis should be carried: Hotspot, threading and HPC analysis.

By doing a hotspot analysis, we can see that the majority of execution time is spent on two functions: **evaluatie_campo_from_point**, calculating the RF field force on a given position, and **point_inside_mesh**, to check if the given position corresponds to a point

¹<https://www.intel.com/content/www/us/en/developer/tools/oneapi/vtune-profiler-download.html?operatingsystem=linux&distributions=online>

²<https://www.intel.com/content/www/us/en/docs/vtune-profiler/tutorial-common-bottlenecks-linux/2020/use-case-and-prerequisites.html#GUID-D1320A0F-E1E9-4A8A-BF53-32535A7368A0>

Figure 8.1: General performance metrics

outside the mesh, that is, a collision. These two functions take 80% and 15% of the total time respectively, and both are called inside `track_1_e`. This still holds true using various threads, or using the other mesh files. The flame graph illustrating this is shown on the top side of Figure 8.2. It is also seen on the bottom side, where the timeline bars appear, that there are multiple blas-threads created at the start of the execution, and that they are only active at the start.

BLAS stands for Basic Linear Algebra Subprograms, they are a collection of subroutines used for different calculations. From the looks of it, being created and only being active at the start (less than 0.5 seconds). I would confirm that they are used by DOLFIN or EIGEN in the background to set up the mesh and certain calculations. Otherwise, the unique thread executing the main part of the code stays active for all execution.

Then, doing a threading analysis, but with 4 threads instead (since my computer has 4 physical cores), we see that the utilization is nearly perfect on Figure 8.3 (3.955 achieved out of expected 4). Also, as seen on Figure 8.4, there is very little overhead, and the threads were working almost all the time. However, that does not mean that a speed-up of 4x was achieved, it was actually a speed-up of 2X (118.371s instead of 237.562s). This speed-up is not realistic, since using the profiler hinders the performance. Profilers often work

Figure 8.2: Hotspots analysis, flame graph view

by inserting additional instrumentation code into the application. This instrumentation collects data about the performance of the application, such as the time spent in each function or memory usage. Aside the fact that the profiler program consumes CPU cycles, some profilers also work by interrupting the application to take measurements, or even wrapping the functions of the program to take start and end time stamps.

Nevertheless, these measurements are a reflection about the difference between core utilization and speed-up. For example, when a core is waiting for synchronization, is inside a critical section or has load balancing issues, in some cases, it can still be scheduled by the OS and consume CPU cycles, therefore appearing active but not doing any effective work. So, even if the cores are 'working' at nearly maximum capacity, the speed-up does not increase much.

Lastly, performing a HPC performance analysis, we see that the timeline bars show pretty much the same activity, and that the physical core optimization is nearly perfect. Again, in this experiment, we see that despite that, the speed-up is just 2.3X (Figures 8.5 and 8.6).

By merging all the information the profiler shows, it appears the use of the cores is correct, but that does not translate into speed-up. We see that activity takes some black zones periodically, likely to the synchronization process between generations and the distribution of the for loop iterations, that is, load balancing. These black regions do not take much

Figure 8.3: Effective CPU utilization with 4 threads

Figure 8.4: Timeline bars showing CPU activity and overhead

time in proportion (<0.6% of activity).

We tried seeing OpenMP regions to determine where exactly was the program most stuck but the profiler could not display any information about these regions. Furthermore, the overhead activity in orange on the timeline bars does not show any overhead activity aside from the first few seconds, so it is safe to assume Intel-VTUNE could not identify OpenMP regions nor OpenMP overhead.

After checking the documentation and some online forums, we saw that other people were having this exact behaviour of not being able to identify OpenMP regions³. Intel offers some instructions to avoid this issue, like configuring drivers⁴⁵, using Intel's C++ compiler or modifying the compilation parameters on CMakeLists.txt⁶, but none resulted

³<https://community.intel.com/t5/Analyzers/Analyze-openmp-program-no-openmp-region-displayed/td-p/1085932?profile.language=es&countrylabel=Latin%20America>

⁴<https://portal.nacad.ufrj.br/online/intel/vtune2017/help/GUID-1FFA3D65-84FA-4426-AC78-7ADFAED1ECOB.html>

⁵<https://portal.nacad.ufrj.br/online/intel/vtune2017/help/GUID-92B13766-1617-44D0-BA70-AC61F5833CA4.html#LINUX>

⁶<https://www.intel.com/content/www/us/en/docs/vtune-profiler/cookbook/2023-2/>

Figure 8.5: General information about HPC analysis

Figure 8.6: Timeline bars and most time hungry functions (all from DOLFIN)

on more information being displayed.

Lastly, we tried repeating these analysis on Priscilla, hoping that a newer processor would

[openmp-imbalance-and-scheduling-overhead.html](#)

provide more information, but the results were the same. This is because Intel only offers the last version of VTUNE for free use, other older versions that would support older processors are available only for paid users, and so older processors like the one in my computer and the one in the Priscilla's node were no longer maintained, thus providing very limited information during the profiling process.

8.2 GPROF-NG profiler

After the limited success obtained in the analysis of the program by VTUNE, we tried other profilers. One of which, was GPROF-NG. This profiler is part of the binutils-2.42 package, and after downloading ⁷ and installing ⁸ it, I followed a tutorial provided on their web to analyze the program ⁹. To collect execution information, and then display it, the steps seen on Listing 8.1 need to be followed.

Listing 8.1: collect application data

```
1 gprofng collect app ./mpc_run data/coaxial_704_01.mpc
2 gprofng display text test.1.er
```

Different parameters gave different insights about the execution. These parameters are added after 'display text', on Listing 8.2 we can see some examples, later studied on their respective figures.

Listing 8.2: Different parameters examples

```
1 gprofng display text -functions test.1.er
2 gprofng display text -metrics ei.totalcpu -source
   run_n_electrons_parallel_thread test.1.er
3 gprofng display text -lines test.1.er
4 gprofng display text -objects test.1.er
5 gprofng display text -fsingle mylagrange_finite_element_0 test.1.er
6 gprofng display text -fsummary test.1.er
7 gprofng display text -threads test.1.er
8 gprofng display gui
```

⁷<https://ftp.gnu.org/gnu/binutils/>

⁸<https://www.linuxfromscratch.org/lfs/view/development/chapter08/binutils.html>

⁹<https://sourceware.org/binutils/docs/gprofng.html#A-Mini-Tutorial>

Each parameter has their own purpose:

- **-functions** is used to request a list of the functions that have been executed, plus their respective CPU times.
- **-metrics** can be used to specify which metrics will be shown. Metrics can be inclusive or exclusive, meaning that they show the time (or CPU cycles or other metric) only for the function at hand or for both the function and child functions respectively.
- **-source** is used to display the source code for a function. By combining this parameter with '-metrics', we can check the requested metric for each line of the function's source code.
- **-lines** is used to print in which line from which file is the function from. Really useful to locate where in the code a certain section is.
- **-objects** lists all the objects that have been referenced. It is useful to see what library and what version have been specifically loaded.
- **-fsingle** provides more information about a function, like size, address, alias, etc.
- **-fsummary** is the same as '-fsingle', but provides that extra information for all functions.
- **-threads** shows the total value of the metrics for each thread.
- **gui** launches the gui version that has to be installed separately ¹⁰.

On Figure 8.7, a simplified output of the command is shown, the total inclusive and exclusive time for each source line of the function `run_n_electrons_parallel` is displayed. In fact, GPROF-NG does not only show the source lines of the specified function, but the source lines of the whole file where the function is defined (if the source code is available, otherwise assembly code will be shown).

On Figure 8.8 we can see a simplified version where all the objects referenced are displayed. This command is useful to check if the program is compiling against the desired libraries.

¹⁰<https://ftp.gnu.org/gnu/gprofng-gui/>

```

1 Current metrics: e.totalcpu:i.totalcpu:name
2 Current Sort Metric: Exclusive Total CPU Time ( e.totalcpu )
3 Source file: mpc_run.cc
4 Object file: mpc_run (found as test.1.er/archives/mpc_run_eP4sFGxpU6)
5 Load Object: mpc_run (found as test.1.er/archives/mpc_run_eP4sFGxpU6)
6
7 Excl.    Incl.
8 Total    Total
9 CPU sec. CPU sec.
10 .....
11 ## 0.060    287.981    1210. EX0 = evaluate_campo_from_point(X[0],X[1],X[2]);
12 .....
13 ## 0.570     0.570    1223. gamma = std::sqrt(1.0 + P[0]*P[0] + P[1]*P[1] + P[2]*P[2]);
14 ## 0.        351.676    1389. std::tie(collision, energy_collision, phase_collision, trayectoria) = track_1_e(energy_inic,power,rf_phase,face,keep);
15 .....
16 ## 0.        353.017    1805. std::tie(face, energy, phase, trayectoria) = run_1_electron(power,erun,efase,energy_0_copy,show);
17 .....
18 ## 0.        353.217    2394. run();
19

```

Figure 8.7: Simplified output of command 'gprofng display text -metrics ei.totalcpu -source run_n_electrons_parallel test.1.er'

```

1 <Unknown> (<Unknown>)
2 <mpc_run> (/home/alejandro/Desktop/Universidad/DIPC/18_gprofng/mpc_run)
3 <libscotcherr-6.so> (/home/alejandro/miniconda3/envs/feics-env/lib/libscotcherr-6.so)
4 <libresolv-2.27.so> (/lib/x86_64-linux-gnu/libresolv-2.27.so)
5 <libkeyutils.so.1.9> (/home/alejandro/miniconda3/envs/feics-env/lib/libkeyutils.so.1.9)
6 <libkrb5support.so.0.1> (/home/alejandro/miniconda3/envs/feics-env/lib/libkrb5support.so.0.1)
7 <libcom_err.so.3.0> (/home/alejandro/miniconda3/envs/feics-env/lib/libcom_err.so.3.0)
8 <libk5crypto.so.3.1> (/home/alejandro/miniconda3/envs/feics-env/lib/libk5crypto.so.3.1)
9 <libkrb5.so.3.3> (/home/alejandro/miniconda3/envs/feics-env/lib/libkrb5.so.3.3)
10 <libquadmath.so.0.0.0> (/home/alejandro/miniconda3/envs/feics-env/lib/libquadmath.so.0.0.0)
11 <libscotch-6.so> (/home/alejandro/miniconda3/envs/feics-env/lib/libscotch-6.so)
12 <libptesmumps-6.so> (/home/alejandro/miniconda3/envs/feics-env/lib/libptesmumps-6.so)
13 <libpord-5.2.1.so> (/home/alejandro/miniconda3/envs/feics-env/lib/libpord-5.2.1.so)
14 <libmumps_common-5.2.1.so> (/home/alejandro/miniconda3/envs/feics-env/lib/libmumps_common-5.2.1.so)
15 <libbtf.so.1.2.6> (/home/alejandro/miniconda3/envs/feics-env/lib/libbtf.so.1.2.6)
16 <libutil-2.27.so> (/lib/x86_64-linux-gnu/libutil-2.27.so)
17 .....

```

Figure 8.8: Simplified output of command 'gprofng display text -objects test.1.er'

```

1 dolfin::Function::eval(Eigen::Ref<Eigen::Matrix<double, -1, 1, 0, -1, 1>, ...) const
2 Exclusive Total CPU Time: 0.580 ( 0.2%)
3 Inclusive Total CPU Time: 282.227 ( 77.6%)
4 Size: 170
5 PC Address: 69:0x00215ae0
6 Source File: (unknown)
7 Object File: (unknown)
8 Load Object: /path/to/feics-env/lib/libdolfin.so.2019.1.0
9 Mangled Name: _ZNK6dolfin8Function4evalEN5Eigen3RefINS1_6Ma...
10 Aliases:
11

```

Figure 8.9: Simplified output of command 'gprofng display text -fsingle dolfin::Function::eval test.1.er'

On Figure 8.9 we see more information about the function *eval* from DOLFIN, this function is used in *evaluate_campo_from_point*, used to determine the force the RF field causes on a certain point. Aside from not so useful information about the memory address, we see that this function in fact takes around 75% of the execution time, in this case specifically, 77.5% (282.227s out of 363.644s), similar to what VTUNE indicated.

```

1  Objects sorted by metric: Exclusive Total CPU Time
2
3  Excl. Total      Name
4  CPU
5  sec.           %
6  608.215 100.00 <Total>
7  151.826 24.96 Process 1, Thread 11
8  150.956 24.82 Process 1, Thread 16
9  150.946 24.82 Process 1, Thread 17
10 150.815 24.80 Process 1, Thread 15
11 0.590 0.10 Process 1, Thread 13
12 0.570 0.09 Process 1, Thread 10
13 0.560 0.09 Process 1, Thread 12
14 0.550 0.09 Process 1, Thread 8
15 0.530 0.09 Process 1, Thread 14
16 0.370 0.06 Process 1, Thread 6
17 0.310 0.05 Process 1, Thread 3
18 0.090 0.01 Process 2, Thread 1
19 0.020 0.00 Process 1, Thread 4
20 0.020 0.00 Process 1, Thread 5

```

Figure 8.10: Simplified output of command `'gprofng display text -threads test.2.er'`

On Figure 8.10 the load balancing between the threads is shown. This shows that various threads are summoned, but mostly four of them in this example (example run with *parallel* = 4) take the majority of execution time, and well balanced also. This does not explain why the speed-up does not escalate as well as it should (later shown on results section).

Lastly, using the gui version gives us a flame graph representation, but the provided information is the same. OpenMP regions are not explored in depth with this profiler, but checking the cpu usage by lines in source code gives us an insight about the hotspots. Nevertheless, the take aways are the same as the ones with VTUNE. Repeating this analysis on Priscilla did not bring any new results.

9. CHAPTER

Result analysis

Each type of mesh requires distinct memory usage, mostly because of the different sizes, thus cache memory requirements differ. So, for each of the following tests, each mesh will be treated independently. Also, the execution can differ greatly depending on the random seed used, the power settings, the initial number of electrons, etc. For the following tests, a similar execution was long for, using different seeds to get similar duration or similar generations, and the same power settings. A counter is used to determine how many time steps were simulated in each experiment, to truly compare execute times, since different number of electrons does not reflect speed-up for their distinct lifespan.

Considering the high number of executions needed to get speed-up results, the parallel execution analysis was done following a guided manner, analyzing one configurable OpenMP parameter at a time and following the next tests using the best results in that parameter. Other possible combination of parameters could achieve better performances, but for the scope of this project and the high demand on ATLAS these tests provide good enough insight.

9.1 Comparing execution times with the Python sequential code

The C++ sequential code ran, on average, 13.8X faster, as seen on Table 9.1. The values are taken as the average of 5 different measurements to get more reliable results. The

speed-up is calculated comparing the time needed per simulation step for the program in each language.

	Coaxial	Pikachu500k	Pikachu900k
Python time (min)	194.9	171.8	162.2
Python steps	148,729,640	140,557,163	132,342,949
C++ time (min)	162.5	228.0	134.7
C++ steps	1,729,110,929	2,555,478,594	1,515,607,554
C++ speed-up	13.9	13.7	13.8

Table 9.1: Comparison of Python and C++ performance

9.2 Comparing execution times of the C++ parallel version

When comparing the C++ sequential version to the parallel one, and since OpenMP was used, there are certain OpenMP configurations that can heavily affect performance.

Since each mesh requires different cache needs, in some cases having threads close to one another can be beneficial, while in other cases it might be worse. Specifically, the *proc_bind* parameter tries to locate threads between the different cores in one way or another. The *proc_bind* settings studied were **false**, **true**, **close** and **spread**.

False does not arrange threads in any particular way, but it allows for thread movement as the OS considers it. **True** does not arrange threads in any way either, and once the threads are created, it does not allow them to switch places. **Close** keeps all threads close to the parent thread, and **spread** is the opposite of that.

As seen on figure 9.1, the overall best performances were achieved by *proc_bind* directives close and true.

As the maximum speed-up did not surpass 6x, and the executions were spending longer and longer waiting in queue because of the increasing ATLAS demand, the following tests did not use all threads from 1 to 32. Instead the most common values between 1 and 16 were tested. The full node was requested nevertheless for each execution.

The next configurable parameter studied was the scheduling type. Since the lifespan of electrons vary depending on the mesh file, load balancing was vital. Each scheduling type is tested with the previous two best *proc_bind* directives.

As seen on Figure 9.2, where for each graph the legend is ordered from best (top) to worst (bottom), the best pairs were *proc_bind* true with guided scheduling for coaxial, and

Figure 9.1: Speed-ups with different `proc_bind` settings for each mesh

`proc_bind` close with dynamic scheduling for both Pikachus. The different pairs achieved similar results on Pikachu. Results were least different in coaxial and most different in Pikachu900k.

Next parameter is the chunk size. When using guided scheduling, OpenMP assigns large portions of the queue, but then reduces those portions as the execution is continued. The given chunk size is the minimum portion size assigned at the end. When using dynamic scheduling, smaller portions are assigned, and as soon as one thread is idle, another portion of the same size is assigned. The chunk size given is the size of the portions assigned.

As seen in Figure 9.3, the optimal chunk sizes for coaxial are 1 and 16. For the Pikachu meshes, the ideal chunk size is 1. In the coaxial piece, there is not much difference between the chunk sizes. In the Pikachu500k mesh, the smaller chunk sizes performed bet-

Figure 9.2: Speed-ups with different scheduling settings for each mesh

ter than the larger chunk sizes, but the difference stays close (<2X difference). On the Pikachu900k mesh, the difference is more noticeable.

9.3 Conclusions

From the different results seen on Figures 9.1, 9.2 and 9.3, we can conclude that load balancing is more of an issue with bigger mesh files, electron lifespans differ more. On these more complex meshes, the overhead of balancing a size 1 chunk size is worth the speed-up achieved, and dynamic scheduling is better. On the other hand, in the coaxial piece, it is not so relevant which scheduling or chunk size to use, as all options perform

Figure 9.3: Speed-ups with different chunk size settings for each mesh

similarly.

However, when placing threads, it is clear that coaxial performs better without the overhead of placing threads close to each other. On both Pikachu pieces, it seems that using *close proc_bind* is slightly better, but the scheduling is a clearer indicative metric for improvement.

The maximum speed-up achieved parallelizing the C++ code was 6x, 8.35x, and 5.45x for coaxial, Pikachu500k, and Pikachu900k respectively. Taking into account the speed-up of the C++ sequential version, the total speed-up achieved was 82x, 114x, and 75x, respectively.

The goal for this project was to port the Python code to C++, and then parallelize the code,

to be able to perform more executions, longer executions or bigger executions in the same time. Taking into account the speed-ups achieved, we can consider that the objectives were fulfilled.

9.4 Future work

Lots of things could be researched with more time in the future to try to obtain better acceleration values. For example, instead of using the legacy version, the code could be adapted to use the new FEniCSx version. Further analysis could be done to try and create a FEniCS installation without MPI support as to try and use MPI to distribute different power settings between nodes.

Changes to the program's logic could be made by removing the need for electron generations, and just use an electron queue where each thread takes/adds electrons with provider-consumer logic.

Lastly, other ATLAS nodes could be used, and more tests carried to find the global optimum values for `proc_bind`, scheduling and chunk size parameters. Even depending on the OpenMP implementation, scheduling policies can change (specially the guided scheduling between the ¹ or ²).

These things require more time and were considered not worth it considering the available time and their priority in regard the project's objectives.

¹<https://github.com/gcc-mirror/gcc/blob/1cb6c2eb3b8361d850be8e8270c597270a1a7967/libgomp/iter.c>

²https://github.com/llvm-mirror/openmp/blob/9c1e6c9bc10be652b92c40129c43c027aad57b6/runtime/src/kmp_dispatch.cpp

Bibliography

- [Beck et al., 2019] Beck, A., Derouillat, J., Lobet, M., Farjallah, A., Massimo, F., Zemzemi, I., Perez, F., Vinci, T., and Grech, M. (2019). Adaptive simd optimizations in particle-in-cell codes with fine-grain particle sorting. *Computer Physics Communications*, 244:246–263.
- [Ben-Zvi et al., 1973] Ben-Zvi, I., Crawford, J. F., and Turneare, J. P. (1973). Electron multiplication in cavities. *IEEE Transactions on Nuclear Science*, 20(3):54–58.
- [Brenner, 2008] Brenner, S. C. (2008). *The mathematical theory of finite element methods*. Springer.
- [Cesare et al., 2020] Cesare, V., Colonnelli, I., and Aldinucci, M. (2020). Practical parallelization of scientific applications. In *2020 28th Euromicro International Conference on Parallel, Distributed and Network-Based Processing (PDP)*, pages 376–384. IEEE.
- [Fajar et al., 2018] Fajar, A., Sarno, R., and Fauzan, A. C. (2018). Comparison of discrete event simulation and agent based simulation for evaluating the performance of port container terminal. In *2018 International Conference on Information and Communications Technology (ICOIACT)*, pages 259–265.
- [Galarza Burguete, 2022] Galarza Burguete, J. (2022). Paralelización de códigos científicos de simulación de partículas.
- [Herlihy et al., 2020] Herlihy, M., Shavit, N., Luchangco, V., and Spear, M. (2020). *The art of multiprocessor programming*. Newnes.
- [Iwasawa et al., 2016] Iwasawa, M., Tanikawa, A., Hosono, N., Nitadori, K., Muranushi, T., and Makino, J. (2016). Implementation and performance of FDPS: a framework for developing parallel particle simulation codes. *Publications of the Astronomical Society of Japan*, 68(4):54.

[Kravchuk et al., 1999] Kravchuk, L., Romanov, G., Tarasov, S., and Paramonov, V. (1999). The computer code for investigation of the multipactor discharge in rf cavities. In *Proceedings of the 1999 Particle Accelerator Conference (Cat. No.99CH36366)*, volume 4, pages 2799–2801 vol.4.

[Pérez et al., 2005] Pérez, F., Lara, J., Galán, L., Alfonseca, M., Montero, I., Román, E., and Raboso, D. (2005). Simulation of multipactor effect through the individual simulation of electrons.

[Shemelin and Belomestnykh, 2020] Shemelin, V. D. and Belomestnykh, S. A. (2020). *Introductory Overview*, pages 1–9. Springer International Publishing, Cham.